

1

yots'enodzida

2

łuk'a

3

notu'

4

kha'ał tr'ekhwneyi

5

k'eddhet

6

k'un' tendeyosrde

2

salmon

1

drone

4

**subsistence
(what we
live on)**

3

**ocean
(salt water)**

6

**spawning
stream, where
fish spawn**

5

**fishing place,
eddy**

7

Tth'itu'

8

no'idelakh

9

ch'etena

10

denigi

11

gath

12

nulaghi

8

they come
back (salmon)

7

Tanana
River

10

moose

9

animal trail

12

chum (dog)
salmon

11

king salmon
(Chinook salmon)

13

sanh tuk'a

14

sanh

15

dɛy'

16

khwyhts'en'

8

summer

7

**coho (Silver)
salmon**

10

fall

9

spring